

Mathematical Aspects of Kinematics of Fluid Flows

San San Htay*

Abstract

In this paper, the flow which is three-dimensional, incompressible and irrotational is considered. Basic concepts for fluid motion are introduced. Streamlines and path lines, the velocity potential at a point, the vorticity vector and irrotational motion are also defined. Using laws of conservation the equation of continuity and Euler's equation of motion are derived, which is concerned some example.

Introduction

Fluid mechanics is the study of the application of the fundamental principles of mechanics to matter in liquid or gases form. The fundamental principles are those of conservation of mass, conservation of energy, Newton's laws of motion. Modern fluid mechanics finds applications in branches of engineering and the physical and medical sciences. It has been evaluated through the interaction of both theoretical and experimental approaches to solving problems.

1. Fluid velocity at a point

At time t a fluid particle is at P , where $\overline{OP} = \underline{r}$ at time $t + \delta t$ the same particle has reached P' where $\overline{OP'} = \underline{r} + \delta \underline{r}$.

Figure. 1

Since the fluid is continuous, we can assume that

$$\underline{q} = \lim_{\delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\delta \underline{r}}{\delta t}$$

$$\underline{q} = \frac{d\underline{r}}{dt}$$

$\underline{q}$ is in general dependent on both $\underline{r}$ and t . So that $\underline{q}$ is a function of time 't' and space $\underline{r}$ (vector) (or) (x, y, z) is scalar.

$$\underline{q} = f(\underline{r}, t)$$

$$= f(x, y, z, t) \text{ (for Cartesian Coordinate)}$$

* Lecturer, Department of Mathematic, Bago University

If $\underline{q} = (q_1, q_2, q_3)$ (or) $\underline{q} = (u, v, w)$ is cartesian coordinates.

$$\underline{q} = q_1 \hat{i} + q_2 \hat{j} + q_3 \hat{k}$$

Since $\underline{r} = x\hat{i} + y\hat{j} + z\hat{k}$

Therefore, $\underline{q} = \frac{d\underline{r}}{dt} = \frac{dx}{dt} \hat{i} + \frac{dy}{dt} \hat{j} + \frac{dz}{dt} \hat{k}$.

1.1 Streamlines and path lines

A curve in the fluid whose tangent is in the direction of the velocity vector $\underline{q}$ is said to be a streamline.

Let $P(x, y, z)$ be a point on the streamline C .

$$\underline{q} = u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} + w\hat{k} \text{ is the velocity at } P.$$

Take the line element $d\underline{r} = dx\hat{i} + dy\hat{j} + dz\hat{k}$.

Then $d\underline{r} \parallel \underline{q} \Rightarrow d\underline{r} \times \underline{q} = \underline{0}$

$$\begin{vmatrix} \hat{i} & \hat{j} & \hat{k} \\ dx & dy & dz \\ u & v & w \end{vmatrix} = \underline{0}$$

$$(w dy - v dz)\hat{i} - (w dx - u dz)\hat{j} + (v dx - u dy)\hat{k} = \underline{0}$$

Therefore, $\frac{dx}{u} = \frac{dy}{v} = \frac{dz}{w}$ is the equation of streamlines for cartesian product.

1.2 The velocity potential

Suppose that at the considered instant t , we can find a scalar function $\phi(x, y, z, t)$ uniform through out the entire field of flow and such that

$$-d\phi = u dx + v dy + w dz$$

$$-\left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} dy + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} dz \right) = u dx + v dy + w dz.$$

Therefore, $u = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}$, $v = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y}$, $w = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z}$.

Since, $\underline{q} = u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} + w\hat{k}$

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{q} &= -\left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \hat{i} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} \hat{j} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \hat{k} \right) \\ &= -\nabla \phi. \end{aligned}$$

ϕ is called velocity potential and the surfaces $\phi(x, y, z, t)$ are called equipotential.

1.3 The vorticity vector and irrotational motion

The vorticity of the fluid motion is defined by $\underline{\zeta} = \text{curl}\underline{q}$.

If $\underline{\zeta} = \underline{0} \Leftrightarrow$ Motion is an irrotational.

So, $\underline{\zeta} = \text{curl}\underline{q} = \underline{0}$.

Let, $\underline{q} = u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} + w\hat{k}$

$$\underline{\nabla} \times \underline{q} = \begin{vmatrix} \hat{i} & \hat{j} & \hat{k} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ u & v & w \end{vmatrix} = \underline{0}$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \right) \hat{i} - \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right) \hat{j} + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \hat{k} = \underline{0}.$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial z}, \quad \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial z}, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}$$

$u dx + v dy + w dz$ must be the exact differential of a function $-\phi$ (say)

$$\begin{aligned} u dx + v dy + w dz &= -d\phi \\ &= -\left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} dy + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} dz \right). \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } u = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}, \quad v = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y}, \quad w = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z}$$

$$u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} + w\hat{k} = -\left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \hat{i} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} \hat{j} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \hat{k} \right)$$

$$\underline{q} = -\underline{\nabla}\phi, \quad \phi = \text{the velocity potential.}$$

In Spherical Coordinate,

$$q_r \hat{r} + q_\theta \hat{\theta} + q_\omega \hat{\omega} = -\left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} \hat{r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \theta} \hat{\theta} + \frac{1}{r \sin \theta} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \omega} \hat{\omega} \right).$$

$$\text{Therefore, } q_r = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r}, \quad q_\theta = -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \theta}, \quad q_\omega = -\frac{1}{r \sin \theta} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \omega}.$$

2. Equation of Continuity

Figure. 2

Let ΔS be a closed surface drawn in the fluid and taken fixed in space. Suppose it contain a volume ΔV of the fluid. Let $\rho = \rho(x, y, z, t)$ be the fluid density (mass per unit volume) at any point (x, y, z) of the fluid in ΔV at any time t .

Suppose $\hat{n}$ is the unit outward drawn normal at any surface element δs of ΔS , where $\delta s \ll \Delta S$. Then if $\underline{q}$ is the fluid velocity at the element, the δS normal component of $\underline{q}$ measured outwards from ΔV is $\hat{n} \cdot \underline{q}$.

Thus, Rate of efflux of fluid mass per unit time across $\delta s = \rho \hat{n} \cdot \underline{q} \delta s$.

Total rate of mass flow out of Δv across

$$\Delta S = \int_{\Delta S} \rho \hat{n} \cdot \underline{q} dS.$$

Total rate of mass flow into $\Delta V = - \int_{\Delta S} \hat{n} \cdot (\rho \underline{q}) dS.$

Using the Gauss's Divergence Theorem $= - \int_{\Delta V} \underline{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \underline{q}) dv.$ (1)

At time t , the mass of fluid within the element is $\int_{\Delta V} \rho dv.$

Local rate of mass increase within

$$\Delta V = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\Delta V} \rho dV = \int_{\Delta V} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} dV. \quad (2)$$

In the absence of sources and sinks within ΔV , matter is not created or destroyed in this region so that from (1) and (2).

$$\int_{\Delta V} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} dV = - \int_{\Delta V} \underline{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \underline{q}) dV$$

(or) $\int_{\Delta V} \left\{ \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \underline{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \underline{q}) \right\} dV = 0$

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \underline{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \underline{q}) = 0, \quad (3)$$

for all volumes.

The above equation is the general equation of continuity which must always hold at any point of a fluid free from sources and sinks.

$$\text{Since } \nabla \cdot (\rho \underline{q}) = \rho \nabla \cdot \underline{q} + \nabla \rho \cdot \underline{q}$$

$$\text{From equation(3) } \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \rho \nabla \cdot \underline{q} + \underline{q} \cdot \nabla \rho = 0$$

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} + \rho \nabla \cdot \underline{q} = 0$$

For incompressible fluid (or) liquid, $\rho = \text{constant}$.

Therefore, Equation of Continuity is $\nabla \cdot \underline{q} = 0$

2.1 Examples

$$(1) \text{ We consider whether or not the motion specified by } \underline{q} = \frac{k^2(\hat{x}\hat{j} - \hat{y}\hat{i})}{x^2 + y^2},$$

($k = \text{constant}$) is a possible motion for an incompressible fluid. If so, determine the equations of the streamlines. Also text whether the motion is of the potential kind and if so determine the velocity potential.

$$\text{Let } \underline{q} = \frac{k^2(\hat{x}\hat{j} - \hat{y}\hat{i})}{x^2 + y^2}$$

$$= k^2 \left(\frac{-y}{x^2 + y^2} \hat{i} + \frac{x}{x^2 + y^2} \hat{j} + 0\hat{k} \right).$$

$$\text{So, } u = \frac{-k^2 y}{x^2 + y^2}, \quad v = \frac{k^2 x}{x^2 + y^2}, \quad w = 0$$

$$\nabla \cdot \underline{q} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z}$$

$$= \frac{2k^2 xy}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} - \frac{2k^2 xy}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} + 0$$

$$= 0.$$

This motion is possible motion for an incompressible fluid.

Equation of streamlines are

$$\frac{dx}{u} = \frac{dy}{v} = \frac{dz}{w}$$

$$\frac{dx}{\frac{-k^2 y}{x^2 + y^2}} = \frac{dy}{\frac{k^2 x}{x^2 + y^2}} = \frac{dz}{0}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \frac{dx}{\frac{-k^2 y}{x^2 + y^2}} = \frac{dy}{\frac{k^2 x}{x^2 + y^2}}$$

$$\frac{dx}{-y} = \frac{dy}{x}$$

$$x dx = -y dy$$

$$x dx + y dy = 0$$

Integrating both sides,

$$\frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{y^2}{2} = c_1$$

$$x^2 + y^2 = c_2 \quad (\text{where } 2c_1 = c_2).$$

Next,

$$\frac{dy}{k^2 x} = \frac{dz}{0}.$$

Therefore $dz = 0$.

So, $z = c_3$.

Thus the streamlines are the curves in which the horizontal planes $z = c_3$ and the cylinder surface $x^2 + y^2 = c_2$.

$$\text{curl } \underline{q} = \underline{\nabla} \times \underline{q}$$

$$= \begin{vmatrix} \hat{i} & \hat{j} & \hat{k} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ \frac{-k^2 x}{x^2 + y^2} & \frac{k^2 y}{x^2 + y^2} & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$= k^2 \left(\frac{x^2 + y^2 - 2x^2}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} + \frac{x^2 + y^2 - 2y^2}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} \right) \hat{k}$$

$$= k^2 \left(\frac{-x^2 + y^2 + x^2 - y^2}{(x^2 + y^2)^2} \right) \hat{k}$$

$$= \underline{0}.$$

Thus the flow is of potential kind.

Therefore, $\underline{q} = -\underline{\nabla} \phi$

$$u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} + w\hat{k} = -\left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \hat{i} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} \hat{j} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \hat{k} \right)$$

The total differential is

$$d\phi = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} dy + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} dz$$

$$d\phi = \frac{k^2 y}{x^2 + y^2} dx - \frac{k^2 x}{x^2 + y^2} dy + 0 dz.$$

Therefore,
$$d\phi = k^2 d(\tan^{-1}(\frac{x}{y})) + \text{constant}$$

By integration, $\phi = k^2 \tan^{-1}(\frac{x}{y})$ (Omitting the constant).

(2) We consider for an incompressible fluid, $\underline{q} = [-wy, wx, 0]$ ($w = \text{constant}$). Also we discuss the nature of the flow.

Since,
$$\underline{q} = [-wy, wx, 0]$$

$$= -wy\hat{i} + wx\hat{j} + 0\hat{k}$$

Equation of streamlines are

$$\frac{dx}{u} = \frac{dy}{v} = \frac{dz}{w}$$

$$\frac{dx}{-wy} = \frac{dy}{wx} = \frac{dz}{0}$$

$$-\frac{dx}{y} = \frac{dy}{x}$$

$$-x dx = y dy$$

$$x dx + y dy = 0.$$

Integrating both sides,

$$\frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{y^2}{2} = c_1$$

$$x^2 + y^2 = c_2 \quad (\text{where } 2c_1 = c_2).$$

Next,
$$\frac{dy}{wx} = \frac{dz}{0}$$

$$dz = 0.$$

Integrating both sides,

$$z = c_3.$$

Thus the streamlines are curves in which the horizontal plane $z = c_3$ and the cylinder surfaces $x^2 + y^2 = c_2$.

(3) We can show that the liquid motion is possible when $u = ax$, $v = ay$, $w = -2az$, and find the streamlines.

Since, $u = ax$, $v = ay$, $w = -2az$

$$\underline{\nabla} \cdot \underline{q} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \hat{i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \hat{j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \hat{k} \right) \cdot (u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} + w\hat{k})$$

$$= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z}$$

$$= a + a - 2a$$

$$= 0$$

Therefore, $\nabla \cdot \underline{q} = 0$.

Therefore, the motion is possible.

The equations of streamlines are

$$\frac{dx}{u} = \frac{dy}{v} = \frac{dz}{w}$$

$$\frac{dx}{ax} = \frac{dy}{ay} = \frac{dz}{-2az}$$

Then

$$\frac{dx}{ax} = \frac{dy}{ay}$$

$$\frac{dx}{x} = \frac{dy}{y}$$

$$\ln x = \ln y + \ln A.$$

$$\ln x - \ln y = \ln A$$

$$\ln \frac{x}{y} = \ln A$$

$$A = \frac{x}{y}.$$

Next, $\frac{dy}{ay} = \frac{dz}{-2az}$

$$2 \frac{dy}{y} = \frac{dz}{-z}$$

$$2 \ln y = -\ln z + \ln B$$

$$\ln y^2 + \ln z = \ln B$$

$$\ln y^2 z = \ln B$$

$$y^2 z = B.$$

2.2 Euler's Equation of Motion

Figure. 3

Consider the portion of fluid contained within any closed surface ΔS and containing a volume ΔV .

Let p = the fluid pressure at δs .

The effect of normal pressure over the surface δs is $p\delta s$.

$$\text{Total pressure over the surface } \Delta S = \int_{\Delta S} \hat{n}P \, dS.$$

By Gauss's Theorem,

$$-\int_{\Delta S} \hat{n}p \, dS = -\int_{\Delta V} \underline{\nabla}p \, dv.$$

Let $\underline{F}$ be the body force per unit mass at any volume element $\delta v (\ll \Delta V)$ of the particle.

The body force (external force) on small element $\delta v = \rho \underline{F} \delta v$, total body force on the entire particle = $\int_{\Delta V} \rho \underline{F} \, dv$.

Since the mass of the volume element δv is $\rho \delta v$, that of the entire fluid particle is $\int_{\Delta V} \rho \, dV$.

But this mass is constant.

Hence, the equation of motion of the fluid particle is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dq}{dt} \int_{\Delta V} \rho \, dV - \int_{\Delta V} \left[\rho \frac{dq}{dt} - \rho \underline{F} + \underline{\nabla}p \right] dV &= 0 \\ &= \int_{\Delta V} (\rho \underline{F} - \underline{\nabla}p) \, dV \end{aligned}$$

$$\int_{\Delta V} \left[\rho \frac{dq}{dt} - \rho \underline{F} + \underline{\nabla}p \right] dV = 0, \text{ since } \Delta V \text{ arbitrary.}$$

$\frac{dq}{dt}$ is the acceleration of the fluid particle following its motion.

$$\rho \frac{dq}{dt} = \rho \underline{F} - \underline{\nabla}p.$$

Therefore,
$$\frac{d\mathbf{q}}{dt} = \mathbf{F} - \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p \quad (4)$$

This is known as an Euler's equation of motion. We have, from Euler's equation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathbf{q}}{dt} &= \mathbf{F} - \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p. \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} + \nabla \frac{q^2}{2} - \mathbf{q} \times \text{curl } \mathbf{q} &= \mathbf{F} - \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla P \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Let the motion be irrotational with velocity potential ϕ and let the external forces be conservative with potential Ω .

Then
$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q} &= -\nabla \phi \\ \mathbf{F} &= -\nabla \Omega \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{q} &= \mathbf{0}. \end{aligned}$$

Substitution in (5),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(-\nabla \phi) + \nabla \frac{q^2}{2} - \mathbf{0} &= -\nabla \Omega - \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla P \\ \nabla \left(-\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \frac{q^2}{2} + \Omega + \frac{P}{\rho} \right) &= \mathbf{0}. \end{aligned}$$

By integrating,

$$-\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \frac{q^2}{2} + \Omega + \frac{P}{\rho} = f(t)$$

which is called Bernoulli's equation.

If the motion is both steady and irrotational,

$$\frac{q^2}{2} + \Omega + \frac{P}{\rho} = C, \quad C = \text{constant}.$$

2.3 Example

Determine the shape of the surface of an incompressible fluid subject to a gravitational field, contained in a cylindrical vessel which rotates about its vertical axis with a constant angular velocity Ω .

Let us take the axis of the cylinder as the z-axis.

The equation of motion is

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} - \mathbf{q} \times \text{curl } \mathbf{q} = -\nabla \left(\frac{1}{2} q^2 + G + \int \frac{dp}{\rho} \right).$$

Since the motion is steady, $\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{0}$.

$$\mathbf{q} = \boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{r} = (\Omega \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \times (r \hat{\mathbf{r}}) = \Omega r \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}},$$

$$\text{curl } \mathbf{q} = \frac{1}{r} \begin{vmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{r}} & r \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} & \hat{\mathbf{k}} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial r} & \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ 0 & \Omega r^2 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$= 2\Omega\hat{k}.$$

$$\underline{q} \times \text{curl}\underline{q} = (\Omega r\hat{\theta}) \times (2\Omega\hat{k}) = 2\Omega^2 r\hat{r}$$

$$\underline{F} = -g\hat{k} = -\underline{\nabla}(gz) = -\underline{\nabla}\Omega.$$

So $\Omega = gz$.

By substitution in equation of motion,

$$2\Omega^2 r\hat{r} = -\underline{\nabla}\left(\frac{1}{2}\Omega^2 r^2 + gz + \frac{p}{\rho}\right)$$

$$\underline{\nabla}(\Omega^2 r^2) = \underline{\nabla}\left(\frac{1}{2}\Omega^2 r^2 + gz + \frac{p}{\rho}\right)$$

$$\Omega^2 r^2 = \frac{1}{2}\Omega^2 r^2 + gz + \frac{p}{\rho} + \text{constant.}$$

$$\frac{p}{\rho} = \frac{1}{2}\Omega^2 r^2 - gz + \text{constant.}$$

At the free surface, p is constant.

Thus, $\frac{1}{2}\Omega^2 r^2 - gz + \text{constant.}$

$$\frac{1}{2}\Omega^2 (x^2 + y^2) - gz = \text{constant.}$$

i.e., $x^2 + y^2 = \frac{2g}{\Omega^2} z + \text{constant.}$

The shapes of the surfaces are parabolids revolution with OZ as its axis, each having latus rectum $\frac{2g}{\Omega^2}$.

2.4 Example

A gass is in steady adiabatic motion along a tube. If q , p , ρ corresponding values of speed, pressure and density, show that, $\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho} = -\frac{q^2}{c^2}$ where

$c^2 = \frac{v p}{\rho}$ gives the local speed of sound.

Equation of motion is

$$\frac{\partial \underline{q}}{\partial t} - \underline{q} \times \text{curl}\underline{q} = -\underline{\nabla}\left(\frac{1}{2}q^2 + G + \int \frac{dp}{\rho}\right). \quad (6)$$

Since the motion is steady, $\frac{\partial \underline{q}}{\partial t} = \underline{0}$.

For the irrotational motion, $\text{curl}\underline{q} = \underline{0}$.

Since there is no body force, $G = 0$.

If the flow is adiabatic,

$p = k\rho^v$ and equation of motion (6) becomes

$$dp = k v \rho^{v-1} d\rho$$

$$\frac{dp}{\rho} = k v \rho^{v-2} d\rho$$

$$\int \frac{dp}{\rho} = \int k v \rho^{v-2} d\rho$$

$$\int \frac{dp}{\rho} = \frac{k v \rho^{v-1}}{v-1}.$$

By substituting in (3), the equation of motion for the adiabatic flow is

$$0 = -\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} q^2 + \frac{k v}{v-1} \rho^{v-1} \right).$$

$$\frac{1}{2} q^2 + \frac{k v}{v-1} \rho^{v-1} = \text{constant}.$$

By differentiating with respect to q , we get

$$q + k v \rho^{v-2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial q} = 0$$

$$k v \frac{\rho^v}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial q} = -q$$

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{v k \rho^v}{\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial q} = -q$$

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{v \rho}{\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial q} = -q$$

$$\frac{1}{\rho} c^2 \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial q} = -q$$

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial q} = -\frac{q}{c^2}.$$

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